
RETHINKING MARITAL CONSENT: A LEGAL AND SOCIAL PERSPECTIVE ON MARITAL RAPE IN INDIA

BY SOUMYA CHAWARE¹ & SRISHTI LAKHOTIA²

ABSTRACT

Marital rape is a challenge and underexplored topic in the larger discourse of gender violence and human rights. This research study examines the historical context, legal structure, and issues surrounding the criminalization of marital rape in India. It investigates the societal norms and legal interpretations that have concealed its status as a crime. The study critically evaluates India's present legal system, identifying loopholes and shortcomings in victim protection. It examines international jurisprudence to better understand how various systems handle marital rape, Challenges including societal shame, a lack of understanding, and resistance. The research investigates the effects of marital rape on victims, highlighting the physical, psychological, and social consequences. It suggests improvements, including legislative changes, improved victim support services, and educational activities to shift society attitudes regarding marital rape. Overall, the research paper will highlight the importance of understanding and addressing marital rape in India.

Keywords: Marital Rape, International Jurisprudence, Indian Penal Code, Patriarchy, Gender Norms, Legal rights

I. INTRODUCTION AND HISTORICAL BACKGROUND OF MARITAL RAPE IN INDIA

Marital rape is also known as Spousal rape. It is having sex with your spouse without getting their permission. In many nations, marital rape is illegal. As part of the marital contract, most states throughout history allowed a husband to have sex with his wife whenever he pleased, up until the 1970s. Even after seven decades of independence, women in India continue to face

¹ Author is a student at University of Mumbai law Academy, Mumbai

² Author is a student at University of Mumbai law Academy, Mumbai

discrimination and lack full freedom and autonomy. Rape in and of itself is a crime against women, a violation of their self-respect and dignity that, when committed inside the confines of a married household, reduces the woman to the position of an object used primarily for sex. In India, marriage is a highly esteemed social institution. Legal consequences of a husband and wife's sexual connection are the most distinctive feature of their union. However, being married is now an authorized excuse for rape. How is a husband allowed to rape his wife? Rape is rape³. If women experience physical, mental, and emotional suffering without access to support, how can the practice of marriage be considered essential? In the concept of marital rape, Indian laws currently are into effect, court cases, the global situation, and the necessity of reviewing marital rape legislation have been addressed in this article in an effort to address Marital rape.

India is gaining recognition for gender equality and women's rights, with advocates calling for the criminalization of marital rape. Critics argue against this due to concerns about legal abuse, government interference, and cultural harm. Despite increased public knowledge, there is still a need for a comprehensive strategy including education, awareness campaigns, support services, and legal changes to empower survivors and challenge patriarchal attitudes that perpetuate this violence. In India, cultural and social elements interact in a complicated way to shape perceptions of marital rape. In India, marriage has historically been seen as a sacred and legally binding agreement, frequently supported by patriarchal conventions that highlight the husband's power and the wife's obligation to submit to him. Due to this cultural framework, consent in marriage is often taken for granted. In addition, women are discouraged from coming forward regarding marital rape due to societal judgment and the belief of family honor, since they fear rejection and reputational damage. These views are reinforced by legal and religious systems that, historically, have not regarded marital rape as a crime. It is difficult to confront marital rape in India because of these variables' combined effects on the normalization of the crime and widespread silence surrounding it.

II. LEGAL FRAMEWORK IN INDIA

Marital rape is viewed and treated differently within the Indian legal system, frequently depending on judicial interpretations. The exemption clause in Section 375 of the Indian Penal Code (IPC) states that "sexual intercourse by a man with his own wife, the wife not being under 15 years of age, is not rape."⁴ This section deals with rape. As a result, the age of the wife

³ <https://blog.ipleaders.in/need-know-marital-rape/>

⁴ Sec. 375 Indian Penal Code, 1860

determines the legal position on marital rape, creating a convoluted web of responsibility and protection.

The Indian Penal Code's Section 376 describes the penalties for rape, which include a fine and a minimum sentence of 7 years in jail, which is renewable to life, or a maximum term of 10 years in jail.

A. Doctrine of Coverture

According to the English common law doctrine known as "coverture," which derives from the French word *couverture*, which means "covering," a married woman's legal existence is deemed to be combined with her husband's. Marital rape is an issue that is primarily affected by the concept of identifying a woman as her husband's.

In the 1860s, when the Indian Penal Code was created, a married woman was not regarded as a separate legal person. In accordance with Victorian patriarchal standards that denied married women the right to own property, did not acknowledge men and women as equals, and combined the identities of husband and wife under the "Doctrine of Coverture."⁵

B. Section 375 of Indian penal code

Section 375 of the Indian Penal Code states that "rape" occurs when a man has sex with a woman in a non-consensual manner, meaning that she cannot give her consent or is under the age of eighteen. This includes penetrating or inserting objects, manipulating body parts, or using the mouth against her will.

Exceptions under Sec 375

1. Medical procedures and interventions do not constitute rape.
2. Sexual intercourse or sexual acts by a man with his own woman, the woman not being under fifteen years of age, isn't rape.⁶

Marital rape, or rape by one spouse against another, is an exception to the consent requirement because, as long as the victim is above 15, marital rape is not illegal in India. Section 375 exception 2 of the Indian Penal Code is discriminatory since it gives husbands broad impunity

⁵ drishtias.com/daily-news-editorials/marital-rape-in-india/print_manually

⁶ Sec 375 Indian Penal Code, 1860

to rape their wives, although under the Code, men who commit crimes against women suffer punishment. Under Section 375 of the Indian Penal Code's Exception 2, there is a violation of the rights to equality and life or personal liberty, as stated in Articles 14 and 21, respectively, of the Indian Constitution.

C. Violation of Article 14

The Indian Constitution's article 14 states that "the State shall not deny to any person equality before the law or equal protection of the laws within territory of India"⁷. Article 14 of the Indian constitution guarantees the right to equality, which is violated by marital rape. Men's acts against their wives are protected by the Exception.

Thus, the Exception permits the mistreatment of married women based only on their marital status while protecting single women from similar mistreatment. Marital law discriminates against married women who are sexually harassed and raped by their husbands by denying them equal protection against such acts. In order to protect single women from rape and other forms of sexual harassment, Section 375 separates married and unmarried women. This is in opposition to Article 14 of the Indian Constitution, which denies equal protection of the law.

Article 14 of the Indian Constitution guarantees equal protection under and before the law for all individuals. However, it allows for logical classification based on intelligible differences and rational nexus. The state's exception to section 375 violates this by making it impossible to distinguish between non-consensual forcible sexual relations, where the perpetrator is a woman's husband and the third person, and criminalizing the former.

D. Violation of Article 21

Every person is entitled to life and personal liberty⁸. The judiciary has occasionally given it profound interpretations that have made it more inclusive and comprehensive. These interpretations include a number of other fundamental rights, including the right to health, the right to sexual privacy, and the right to bodily self-determination, all of which are explicitly infringed by the section 375 exception 2.

⁷ Indian Constitution art. 14

⁸ Indian Constitution art. 21

The Supreme Court associated the right to choose one's sexual behaviour with the constitutional rights to personal liberty, privacy, dignity, and physical integrity in *Suchita Srivastava v. Chandigarh Administration* case⁹.

The Supreme Court announced that everyone has the fundamental right to privacy in case of *Justice K.S. Puttuswamy (Retd.) v. Union of India*¹⁰ and stated that the freedom to make private decisions, mainly pertaining to one's sexual or procreative nature and decisions regarding intimate contacts, is embodied in the right to decisional privacy. The Supreme Court has acknowledged the right of all women to refrain from sexual activity, regardless of their marital status, as a basic right granted by Article 21 of the Constitution in each of these judgements.

Furthermore, the Supreme Court noted in the case of *Joseph Shine v. Union of India*¹¹ that a woman is not a piece of property or chattel owned by men and that all women have the unalienable right to sexual autonomy, regardless of their marital status. Consequently, under article 21, coerced sexual cohabitation is considered a violation of fundamental rights.

III. MARITAL RAPE AND INTERNATIONAL JURISPRUDENCE

Marital rape laws differ widely between countries, reflecting differences in social, legal, and cultural perspectives. While some nations have laws that explicitly prohibit marital rape, others may not, providing survivors with little protection. In certain locations, the legal system is evolving to better address the complex issues of marriage and consent.

- Areas with Explicit Criminalization of Marital assault:

Western nations such as the US, Canada, UK, and Europe have made marital rape a crime, highlighting the significance of consent in marriage. While Australia and India have partially criminalized it, countries like Sweden, Canada, and the UK have made substantial moves in that direction. Marital rape remains unpunished or ineffectual in certain nations, nevertheless, as cultural and traditional beliefs continue to take place over the rights and welfare of the individual.

- Legal perspective in Asia:

⁹ *Suchita Srivastava v. Chandigarh Administration* (2009) 14 SCR 989, (2009) 9 SCC 1

¹⁰ *Justice K.S. Puttuswamy (Retd.) v. Union of India* (2017) 10 SCC 1, AIR 2017 SC 4161

¹¹ *Joseph Shine v. Union of India* (2019) 3 SCC 39, AIR 2018 SC 4898

A wide variety of legal perspectives on marital rape are available in Asia. While some nations, such as Singapore and India, have recognized the significance of making marital rape a crime, and other nations such as Afghanistan and Iran, may not have done so or may have legal systems that are insufficiently responsive to the problem. Asia's legal discourse on marital rape is a reflection of the complex relations between evolving societal attitudes, convictions concerning religion, and cultural traditions.

- **Marital Rape in Bangladesh:**

Due to a lack of explicit legislation, the legal landscape in Bangladesh involving marital rape is still being debated. Victims of rape who are not married or who are committed by strangers are not given justice under the Penal Code. Social norms and cultural traditions that uphold patriarchal beliefs and place women in inferior roles within marriages worsen this lack of recognition.

- **Marital Rape in USA:**

Marital rape is a crime in the United States, but it was not always lawful. According to English common law, a man could not lawfully rape his wife without her consent. The traditional belief that wives are their husbands' property and the husband's "right to sex" are part of the British common law perspective that is applied in the US. Today, marital rape is illegal in more than 50 states. Texas, California, and South Carolina are three states that have criminalized marital rape. Spousal rape is specifically included under South Carolina's laws, and spousal rape is now illegal in all 50 states, safeguarding women's legal equality and dignity.¹²

IV. CHALLENGES IN CRIMINALIZING MARITAL RAPE IN INDIA

The issue of marital rape in India is complex due to the lack of a uniform legal definition. Despite some progress in recognizing certain forms of sexual violence, the lack of a comprehensive definition makes it difficult to prosecute offenders and protect survivors, leading to inconsistent judgments and uncertainty in cases involving marital rape.¹³

A. Social and cultural challenges

¹² <https://www.ijlra.com/paper-details.php?isuurl=marital-rape-a-comparative-legal-analysis-by-nending-sonia->

¹³ Exploring Concerns Associated with Marital Rape in India: An In-Depth Legal Analysis

1. Deep- rooted Social Stigma & Cultural Barriers:

Marital rape in India is often concealed by social stigma and misconceptions, with many believing consent is implied, leading to underreporting. Raising awareness and challenging traditional norms is crucial for effectively addressing the issue and breaking down societal barriers.

2. Disgrace and Honour:

Talking about sex and sexual assault is not always acceptable. Marital rape victims may be reluctant to report the crime out of fear of social disgrace and possible harm to their family's reputation.

3. Victim Blaming:

There's a widespread culture that holds wives accountable for their husbands' misdeeds. This stigma makes it even harder for women to come forward.

4. Sacredness of Marriage:

In Indian culture, marriage is frequently seen as an indissoluble and sacred union. The notion that rape can take place in this hallowed establishment contradicts widely held views regarding marriage.

5. Lack of Awareness:

Due to a lack of knowledge and education regarding sexual rights and consent, many people, especially women, may not see non-consensual sex inside marriage as rape.

6. Legal Recognition:

Marital rape has not always been regarded as a crime by India's legal system. If the wife is older than a specific age, husbands who rape their spouses are not prosecuted under the Indian Penal Code. The cultural norms that see marital rape as non-existent or acceptable are reinforced by this legal inaction.

7. Opposition from Conventional Institutions:

Community and religious leaders frequently have a big influence on public opinion and legislation. Because they see changes to marital rape legislation as a threat to traditional values and family systems, these leaders may oppose such changes.

8. Unregistered and Insufficient Documentation of Marital Rape:

Underreporting and lack of documentation of marital rape cases is a significant challenge, largely due to societal pressures, fear of retaliation, and lack of support, which hinders understanding the problem's extent and hinders the formulation of effective policies and interventions.

B. Issues of Evidence & Prosecution in Marital Rape

1. Legal Structure:

In Present Legal Situation if the victim is a woman over the age of 18, marital rape is not punishable by Section 375 of the Indian Penal Code (IPC),¹⁴ which poses a serious obstacle to prosecution and a law that is inconsistent with making Marital rape as a crime is “The Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act (PWDVA), 2005¹⁵”, provides victims of domestic violence with civil remedies, but it does not criminalize marital rape. The process of gathering evidence in cases of marital rape can be challenging due to the private nature of the crime and delayed reporting. Victims may be hesitant to undergo medical examinations due to fear of stigma or consequences, and repeatedly having sex can complicate proving voluntary conduct.

2. Witnesses and Testimonies:

Victims' testimony is critical but frequently challenged, particularly in cases of marital discord. Victims may be discouraged from speaking out due to family and social pressures. Furthermore, because of the rarity of direct witnesses in cases of hidden marital rape, circumstantial evidence from friends or relatives is insufficient for prosecution.

3. Consent and Force:

In terms of marital rape, two prevalent approaches are gratitude consent and coercion. Gratitude consent is difficult to show since society norms regard marital sex as an obligation, whereas coercion and intimidation are more widespread but more difficult to demonstrate.

4. Judiciary and Law Enforcement:

Insensitivity or training may influence police responses to marital rape, resulting in potential bias or disbelief. Judicial bias, in which judges see matters as private affairs, may also inhibit conviction in such cases due to traditional marriage beliefs.

5. Systems of Support:

Victims of marital rape face challenges in seeking justice due to limited access to legal, medical, and psychological support services, and financial dependency, making it difficult for women to file lawsuits against their spouses.

¹⁴ Sec. 375 Indian Penal Code, 1860

¹⁵ The Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act (PWDVA), 2005

C. The role of Patriarchy & gender norms

1. Conventional marital practices

In patriarchal societies, women are often subordinated to their husbands, leading to a power imbalance where wives must satisfy their husbands' sexual demands without their consent. Marital duty is also often seen as a wife's responsibility, implying that marriage grants unlimited sexual access to the wife, questioning the concept of consent.

2. Ownership Perception

In patriarchal countries, wives are often seen as property, leading to the belief that husbands have authority to manage their bodies. This view makes understanding marital rape difficult. Additionally, patriarchal standards often lead to the belief that marriage requires continuous assent to sexual behaviour, undermining women's independence and right to decline sex during marriage.

3. Stereotypes and Beliefs in Community

Women who report marital rape endure societal stigma and victim blaming since patriarchal society frequently denies their character or behavior. Fear of social exclusion is also a factor, as women may be hesitant to share their experiences due to the significance of maintaining family honor in patriarchal cultures.

4. Reaction of Law Enforcement

Law enforcement officers may lack empathy and knowledge when dealing with situations of marital rape, which could result in harsh treatment or skeptical views. Furthermore, patriarchal ideas may lead authorities to be reluctant to intervene, regarding the situation as a private matter.

V. IMPACT ON THE VICTIMS

Marital rape can have severe physical, psychological, and mental health consequences for the victimized woman. These issues include feelings of melancholy, PTSD, anxiety, low self-esteem, and rape trauma syndrome.¹⁶ Women who have been raped in marriage are often expected to satisfy their husband's sexual desires without her consent, which can be frightening for them. They worry about the potential damage to their family's reputation and the pressure to provide for them.

¹⁶ <https://journals.plos.org/globalpublichealth>

Most women experience chronic pain due to their numerous rapes, leading to knife wounds, broken ribs, black eyes, and body marks. Victims may also experience discomfort and bleeding vaginally due to a severe vaginal rupture. Recalling the maltreatment incident can lead to illness and unintended pregnancies, further straining their mental and emotional health.¹⁷

Victims of marital rape may endure premature delivery and infertility, which could have a severe impact on their future plans to start a family. Victims of rape may be urged to commit suicide because of their feelings about the assault and their helplessness to disclose it. Victims often experience social isolation, trust issues, and cultural and societal standards placing blame on them, resulting in feelings of guilt and shame. The stigma attached to marital rape or their spouse's controlling behaviour can also negatively impact relationships and the victim's ability to report the abuse.

VI. REFORMS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The suggested legislative reforms to address marital rape include changing current laws to expressly identify and acknowledge it as a crime, emphasizing consent, safeguarding victims identity and dignity, and providing specialized support services. NGOs and civil society play an important role in advocacy by conducting awareness campaigns, policy advocacy, support networks, research, and educational initiatives. These include incorporating consent education into curriculum at schools, conducting community workshops, running media campaigns to promote positive messages about consent and respectful relationships, and collaborating with religious and community leaders to develop a culture of respect and equality. Research will serve to shape lobbying and policy activities, while educational programs will emphasize gender equality and healthy relationships.

Addressing marital rape within legal frameworks necessitates a holistic approach that considers both legislative measures and societal attitudes. First, legislative measures are required to ensure that marital rape is recognized as a criminal offense, giving victims with legal redress and protection. This includes eliminating any marital immunity clauses in existing laws and clearly criminalizing nonconsensual sexual conduct within marriage. Furthermore, legislation should be changed to guarantee that the age of consent is applied similarly to all individuals,

¹⁷ <https://www.legalserviceindia.com/legal/article-9414-marital-rape-a-harsh-reality-behind-closed-doors.html>

regardless of marital status, thereby safeguarding minors against sexual exploitation within marriage.

The J.S. Verma Report is the landmark report that reignited the debate on marital rape in recent times. The group proposed a four-pronged method for successfully criminalizing marital rape.¹⁸ It asked for the removal of the exemption clause, it asked to specifically mention that it is not a defence, that there would not be a presumption of consent and lastly, that the amount of penalty will be the same. The same should be done to effectively deal with marital rape in India.

Additionally, section 375 of the IPC should be amended to omit explanation (2). The same legal standards that apply to physical violence committed by a husband against his wife also apply to forced sexual relations between a husband and wife. The deletion of section 376 A was justified by the same logic in the same report i.e. 172nd report of Law Commission of India¹⁹.

Furthermore, judicial activism is required to interpret existing legal provisions in a way that protects individual's rights and dignity, particularly the right to bodily autonomy and the freedom from sexual assault in married relationships. Courts should interpret constitutional provisions, such as Article 21, broadly to include the freedom to refuse sexual intercourse and be free of unwelcome sexual behaviour, so creating a strong legal foundation for dealing with marital rape.

VII. CONCLUSION

Marital rape is still not considered a crime in India, despite continuous debates and proposals for legal reform. The Indian Penal Code (IPC) exempts a husband from rape charges if the woman is beyond the age of 15. This exclusion has been extensively condemned as discriminatory and a violation of women's constitutional rights.

In contrast, several other nations have criminalized marital rape and offered legal protection to women in violent marriages. The situation in India differs from those of these countries, highlighting the need for legal change to deal with marital rape. The continuous discussion and requests for reform reflect the changing social and cultural realities in India, as well as the need for a more progressive and gender-sensitive strategy to address sexual assault and abuse.

¹⁸ J.S. Verma Report, *supra* note 32, 117.

¹⁹ 172nd report of Law Commission of India on Review of Rape Laws, March 2000, para 3.1.2.1